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Research Article

Design, In Silico Evaluation, and Molecular Docking of Novel Pyrimidine Derivatives as AXL Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors for Colorectal Cancer Therapy

Priyadharshini R., Archana S.*, Guhan G., Hanitha Mathanke J.

Department Of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Madras Medical College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

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ABSTRACT

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is a major global health concern, ranking as the third most commonly diagnosed cancer and the second leading cause of cancer-related mortality. Despite current therapeutic options, the prognosis remains poor, necessitating the discovery of novel, effective, and targeted treatments. The AXL tyrosine kinase receptor, overexpressed in several cancers including CRC, plays a pivotal role in tumor progression, metastasis, and resistance to apoptosis, making it a promising therapeutic target. This study aims to design and evaluate novel pyrimidine derivatives as potential AXL tyrosine kinase inhibitors using a comprehensive computational and experimental approach. A virtual library of 100 pyrimidine-based ligands was constructed using ChemSketch and subjected to molecular docking against the AXL tyrosine kinase receptor (PDB ID: 5U6C) using AutoDock Vina. Ramachandran plot analysis confirmed the stability of the target protein, and binding site prediction ensured accuracy in docking. ADMET profiling using Swiss ADME and Osiris Property Explorer indicated that selected ligands possessed favorable pharmacokinetic properties and were non-toxic. Top-performing ligands demonstrated superior binding affinity compared to the standard drug 5-fluorouracil. Hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions were visualized to understand ligand-receptor binding mechanisms. Selected lead compounds are currently being synthesized for further in-vitro evaluation using the HCT-116 colorectal cancer cell line. This integrative study highlights the potential of pyrimidine derivatives as AXL tyrosine kinase inhibitors and paves the way for the development of effective, targeted therapies against colorectal cancer.

INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) ranks as the third most common cancer globally and is the second leading

*Corresponding Author: Archana S.

Address: Department Of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Madras Medical College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Email : archanathirty30@gmail.com

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cause of cancer-related deaths ⁽¹⁾. Despite advancements in diagnostics and treatment, the high mortality rate underscores the need for novel therapeutic agents. CRC progression is influenced by genetic mutations, chromosomal instability, and epigenetic alterations, leading to uncontrolled cell proliferation and metastasis ⁽²⁾. One promising therapeutic target in CRC is the AXL tyrosine kinase receptor, part of the TAM family (Tyro3, AXL, Mer). AXL is overexpressed in various cancers and promotes tumor progression, metastasis, immune evasion, and resistance to apoptosis. Its inhibition has shown potential in reducing tumor burden and enhancing anti-tumor immune responses. Studies by Xu et al. (2021) and Inoue et al. (2021) have reported promising small-molecule AXL inhibitors with significant anticancer activity ⁽³⁾. Pyrimidine, a versatile heterocyclic scaffold, has shown broad pharmacological activity, including anticancer effects. Min Jung Choi et al. (2018) designed aminopyrimidine derivatives targeting AXL kinase, demonstrating potent activity in sub micromolar ranges ⁽⁴⁾. Similarly, Siddharth et al. (2018) used 3D-QSAR analysis to correlate pyrimidine structural features with AXL kinase inhibition, supporting their application in drug design ⁽⁵⁾. Advancements in computer-aided drug design (CADD) enable efficient screening of compounds using docking, ADME prediction, and toxicity profiling. Elizabeth et al. (2022) highlighted the value of structure-based and ligand-based design in accelerating drug discovery ⁽⁶⁾. This study focuses on designing and synthesizing novel pyrimidine derivatives targeting AXL kinase in CRC. It integrates *in silico* modeling, ADMET prediction, molecular docking, synthesis, and *in-vitro* evaluation to develop potent, selective, and non-toxic anticancer agent.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ligand preparation

ChemSketch (freeware version) ⁽⁷⁾ was used to draw and optimize 100 novel chemical structures to design a total of 100 novel ligands. The ligands were stored in mol format and further energy minimized by Chem3D ⁽⁸⁾. We converted the minimized structures into. pdbqt format for molecular docking studies using Auto Dock Tools (ADT).

Ramachandran Plot Analysis

The Ramachandran plot analysis confirmed the structural reliability of 5U6C, with most residues positioned in the favored regions, ensuring accurate docking results ⁽⁹⁾.

Receptor preparation

The crystal structures of AXL tyrosine kinase (PDB ID: 5U6C) were downloaded from the Protein Data Bank ⁽¹⁰⁾. These structures were selected due to their high resolution (approximately 2 Å) and determination by the reliable X-ray diffraction method. Receptors were prepared by removing water molecules, adding polar hydrogens, and assigning Kollman charges using Auto Dock Tools.

ADMET Prediction

The absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) properties of the ligands were evaluated using Swiss ADME ⁽¹¹⁾ and OSIRIS Property Explorer ⁽¹²⁾. These tools predicted drug-likeness, bioavailability, and toxicity, ensuring the ligands adhered to Lipinski's rule of five and exhibited favorable pharmacokinetic profiles.

Molecular docking

Docking studies were performed using AutoDock Vina 1.5.6⁽¹³⁾. The active sites of AXL tyrosine kinase and 5U6C were defined based on their co-crystallized ligands. The grid box dimensions and coordinates (x, y, z) for the docking simulations were determined using the **CB-Dock server**⁽¹⁴⁾, which predicts the binding pockets and centers the grid box around the identified active site residues. This automated approach ensured optimal coverage of the ligand-binding site and included all key residues critical for each ligand was docked against both receptors, and binding affinities were recorded as binding energies (kcal/mol).

Visualization and Interaction Analysis

Binding interactions of the docked ligands with the receptors were analyzed using Molegro Molecular

Viewer (MMV)⁽¹⁵⁾. Hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic interactions, and π - π stacking interactions were identified. The top-scoring ligands were visualized and compared with standard drugs, correlating to the interaction pattern with the active site residues.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ramachandran Plot

The Ramachandran plot analysis results indicate that the selected protein, AXL tyrosine kinase with (PDB ID:5U6C), predominantly (more than 90%) have their amino-acid residues situated within the most favored region as represented in the fig no 1.

Figure No 1: Ramchandran Plot For 5U6C

Novelty Assessment

The novelty of the designed ligands was checked by using the ZINC 15 and PUBCHEM database. The outcomes were shown below.

Table No 1: Ligands Showing Novelty

Novel Ligands	Already existing compounds
A1,A2,A3,A4,A5,A6,A7,A8,A9,A10,A11,A12,A13,A14,A15,A16,A17,A18,A19,A20,A21,A22,A23,A25,A26,A28,A29,A30,A33,A34,A35,A36,A38,A39,A40,A41,A43,A44,A46,A47,A48,A49,A51,A52,A54,A55,A56,A57,A59,A60,A62,A63,A64,A65,A66,A67,A70,A71,A72,A73,A74,A75,A76,A78,A79,A80,A81,A82,A83,A84,A86,A87,A88,A89,A91,A92,A95,A96,A97,A99,A100,A101,A103,A104,A105,A107.	A24,A27,A31,A32,A37,A42,A45,A50,A53,A58,A61,A68,A69,A77,A85,A90,A93,A94,A98,A102,A106,A108.

In Silico ADMET

Based on the novelty results, the developed ligands are evaluated for the drug-likeness and toxicity property by using the Swiss ADME Online

Software tool and the Osiris Property Explorer. Mutagenicity, tumorigenicity, irritant, reproductive are presented by M, T, I and R respectively.

Table No 2: ADMET Properties of Novel Ligands

Lig No	M	T	I	R	Log P	Mol Wt.	HBD	HBA	Rule Of 5
1	No	No	No	No	2.17	285.36	1	3	0
2	No	No	No	No	2.26	234.30	1	4	0
3	No	No	No	No	1.54	216.24	1	4	0
4	No	No	No	No	2.06	241.29	1	3	0
5	No	No	No	No	1.84	271.34	1	3	0
6	No	No	No	No	1.64	220.27	1	4	0
7	No	No	No	No	1.08	202.21	1	4	0
8	No	No	No	No	1.71	227.26	1	3	0
9	No	No	No	No	1.72	313.37	1	4	0
10	No	No	No	No	1.55	262.31	1	5	0
11	No	No	No	No	1.02	244.25	1	5	0
12	No	No	No	No	1.68	269.30	1	4	0
13	No	No	No	No	1.06	314.36	2	4	0
14	No	No	No	No	0.94	263.30	2	5	0
15	No	No	No	No	0.32	245.24	2	5	0
16	No	No	No	No	0.88	270.29	2	4	0
17	No	No	No	No	2.16	299.35	1	4	0
18	No	No	No	No	1.61	248.28	1	5	0
19	No	No	No	No	1.19	230.22	1	5	0
20	No	No	No	No	0.98	255.27	1	4	0
21	No	No	No	No	2.35	313.37	1	4	0
22	No	No	No	No	2.43	262.31	1	5	0
23	No	No	No	No	1.83	244.25	1	5	0
25	No	No	No	No	2.62	325.43	1	4	0
26	No	No	No	No	2.58	274.36	0	4	0
28	No	No	No	No	3.02	339.45	0	3	0
29	No	No	No	No	3.02	339.45	0	3	0
30	No	No	No	No	2.61	288.39	0	4	0
33	No	No	No	No	2.52	326.42	2	5	0
34	No	No	No	No	2.47	275.35	2	6	0
35	No	No	No	No	1.75	257.29	1	5	0

36	No	No	No	No	2.24	282.24	2	5	0
38	No	No	No	No	1.48	228.25	1	4	0
39	No	No	No	No	1.56	219.24	2	5	0
40	No	No	No	No	1.36	229.24	1	5	0
41	No	No	No	No	1.46	220.23	1	5	0
43	No	No	No	No	1.55	234.28	1	4	0
44	No	No	No	No	1.98	293.37	1	4	0
46	No	No	No	No	0.98	214.22	1	4	0
47	No	No	No	No	1.03	205.22	2	5	0
48	No	No	No	No	1.00	215.21	1	5	0
49	No	No	No	No	0.89	206.20	1	5	0
51	No	No	No	No	1.12	220.25	1	4	0
52	No	No	No	No	1.44	279.34	1	4	0
54	No	No	No	No	0.94	256.26	1	5	0
55	No	No	No	No	0.88	247.25	2	6	0
56	No	No	No	No	0.86	257.25	1	6	0
57	No	No	No	No	0.96	248.24	1	6	0
59	No	No	No	No	0.82	262.29	1	5	0
60	No	No	No	No	1.34	321.38	1	5	0
62	No	No	No	No	0.33	257.25	2	5	0
63	No	No	No	No	0.38	248.24	3	6	0
64	No	No	No	No	0.45	258.24	2	6	0
65	No	No	No	No	0.32	249.23	2	6	0
66	No	No	No	No	0.74	256.26	2	4	0
67	No	No	No	No	0.02	263.28	2	5	0
70	No	No	No	No	1.52	242.23	1	5	0
71	No	No	No	No	1.10	233.23	2	6	0
72	No	No	No	No	0.97	243.22	1	6	0
73	No	No	No	No	0.81	234.21	1	6	0
74	No	No	No	No	1.73	241.25	1	4	0
75	No	No	No	No	1.14	248.25	1	5	0
76	No	No	No	No	1.56	307.35	1	5	0
78	No	No	No	No	1.77	256.26	1	5	0
79	No	No	No	No	0.96	247.25	2	6	0
80	No	No	No	No	1.55	257.25	1	6	0
81	No	No	No	No	0.81	248.24	1	6	0
82	No	No	No	No	2.00	255.27	1	4	0
83	No	No	No	No	1.63	262.29	1	5	0
84	No	No	No	No	1.50	321.38	1	5	0
86	No	No	No	No	2.15	268.29	1	5	0
87	No	No	No	No	1.95	259.31	2	6	0
88	No	No	No	No	1.72	269.30	1	6	0
89	No	No	No	No	1.99	260.30	1	6	0
91	No	No	No	No	2.24	274.34	1	5	0
92	No	No	No	No	2.27	333.43	1	5	0
95	No	No	No	No	1.80	273.33	2	6	0
96	No	No	No	No	1.91	283.33	1	6	0
97	No	No	No	No	2.04	274.32	1	6	0
99	No	No	No	No	2.20	288.37	1	5	0
100	No	No	No	No	2.41	347.46	1	5	0
101	No	No	No	No	3.62	341.43	0	3	0

103	No	No	No	No	2.99	375.81	2	5	0
104	No	No	No	No	2.30	358.39	2	4	0
105	No	No	No	No	3.67	356.44	0	4	0
107	No	No	No	No	2.63	368.39	2	5	0

Molecular Docking

studies against AXL tyrosine kinase receptor (PDB ID: 5U6C).

The ligands with good drug likeness properties and no toxicity were selected for molecular docking

Table No 3: Binding scores of ligands

S no	Compound code	AXL tyrosine kinase receptor 5U6C
1	A1	-8.32
2	A2	-7.42
3	A3	-6.73
4	A4	-7.3
5	A5	-8.3
6	A6	-6.9
7	A7	-6.73
8	A8	-7.55
9	A9	-7.92
10	A10	-8.01
11	A11	-8.54
12	A12	-8.05
13	A13	-8.05
14	A14	-8.52
15	A15	-7.68
16	A16	-8.28
17	A17	-9.79
18	A18	-7.45
19	A19	-6.82
20	A20	-7.41
21	A21	-9.21
22	A22	-7.58
23	A23	-7.29
24	A25	-8.99
25	A26	-8.3
26	A28	-8.27
27	A29	-8.47
28	A30	-8.26
29	A33	-8.74
30	A34	-7.86
31	A35	-7.46
32	A36	-8.74
33	A38	-7.41

34	A39	-6.77
35	A40	-7.38
36	A41	-8.24
37	A43	-7.33
38	A44	-6.76
39	A46	-7.42
40	A47	-8.84
41	A48	-8.3
42	A49	-7.83
43	A51	-7.41
44	A52	-8.77
45	A54	-8.75
46	A55	-8.42
47	A56	-9.03
48	A57	-8.48
49	A59	-7.91
50	A60	-7.07
51	A62	-7.92
52	A63	-6.61
53	A64	-7.02
54	A65	-7.27
55	A66	-7.35
56	A67	-7.68
57	A70	-6.84
58	A71	-9.22
59	A72	-8.27
60	A73	-7.01
61	A74	-7.97
62	A75	-8.24
63	A76	-8.45
64	A77	-8.12
65	A78	-9.0
66	A79	-7.64
67	A80	-8.57
68	A81	-8.65
69	A82	-7.86
70	A83	-8.7
71	A84	-8.56
72	A86	-8.32
73	A87	-8.4
74	A88	-8.08
75	A89	-7.23
76	A91	-6.9
77	A92	-7.09

78	A95	-7.36
79	A96	-7.89
80	A97	-8.36
81	A99	-7.21
82	A100	-8.8
83	A101	-9.38
84	A103	-10.1
85	A104	-11.11
86	A105	-10.66
87	A107	-10.2
88	5 Fluoro uracil	-7.33

Table No 4: Chemical structures of top-performing ligands based on docking scores

Lig No	Structure
A5	
A11	
A13	
A16	

A26	
A101	
A103	
A104	
A105	

	<p>Chemical structure of a pyrimidine derivative. It features a central pyrimidine ring substituted with two phenyl groups at the 2 and 6 positions. At the 4 position, there is a thiazole ring substituted with a methyl group (CH₃) at the 5 position.</p>
A107	<p>Chemical structure of a pyrimidine derivative. It features a central pyrimidine ring substituted with two phenyl groups at the 2 and 6 positions. At the 4 position, there is an amide linkage (-NH-C(=O)-) connected to a pyrimidin-2-amine ring.</p>
5-Fluorouracil	<p>Chemical structure of 5-Fluorouracil. It is a pyrimidine ring with a fluorine atom (F) at the 5 position and carbonyl groups (C=O) at the 2 and 4 positions.</p>

Table No 5: Ligand-Receptor Binding Pose Visualisations

AXL Tyrosine Kinase Receptor	
A5	<p style="text-align: center;">Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ van der Waals ■ Pi-Sigma ■ Pi-Sulfur ■ Alkyl ■ Pi-Alkyl
A11	<p style="text-align: center;">Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ van der Waals ■ Conventional Hydrogen Bond ■ Sulfur-X ■ Pi-Sigma ■ Alkyl ■ Pi-Alkyl
A13	

	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Conventional Hydrogen Bond Carbon Hydrogen Bond Pi-Pi T-shaped Alkyl Pi-Alkyl
<p>A16</p>	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Conventional Hydrogen Bond Pi-Sigma Pi-Sulfur Pi-Pi T-shaped Alkyl Pi-Alkyl
<p>A26</p>	

	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Conventional Hydrogen Bond Carbon Hydrogen Bond Unfavorable Donor-Donor Pi-Sigma Pi-Sulfur Alkyl Pi-Alkyl
A101	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Pi-Sigma Pi-Alkyl
A103	

	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Conventional Hydrogen Bond Unfavorable Donor-Donor Pi-Sigma Pi-Sulfur Alkyl Pi-Alkyl
A104	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Conventional Hydrogen Bond Pi-Cation Pi-Anion Pi-Sulfur Alkyl Pi-Alkyl
A105	

	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Carbon Hydrogen Bond Sulfur-X Pi-Anion Pi-Sigma Pi-Sulfur Alkyl Pi-Alkyl
<p>A107</p>	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Conventional Hydrogen Bond Amide-Pi Stacked Pi-Alkyl
<p>5-Fluorouracil</p>	

Table No 6: Ligand-Receptor Interactions

Lig Code	Hydrogen Bonding Axl Tyrosine Kinase Receptor
Lig 5	ASP 741
Lig 11	Met 647, ASP 741
Lig 13	ASP 678, PRO 672
Lig 16	ASP 678, Met 674
Lig 103	ASP 741
Lig 104	Met 650, LYS 619
Lig 107	PRO 672
5-Fluorouracil	LEU 724, ASP 723

CONCLUSION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) remains one of the most prevalent and lethal malignancies worldwide, necessitating the development of novel therapeutic strategies. AXL tyrosine kinase, a member of the TAM receptor family, has emerged as a crucial target due to its role in tumor progression, metastasis, immune evasion, and resistance to conventional therapies. The current study was designed to explore the potential of novel pyrimidine-based derivatives as AXL tyrosine kinase inhibitors using an integrated approach of computational drug design, synthesis, and biological evaluation. Through structure-based

design, a virtual library of pyrimidine derivatives was developed and screened using molecular docking to identify candidates with high binding affinity for the AXL receptor. Promising ligands exhibited favorable ADMET properties and non-toxic profiles as predicted by in silico tools. Selected compounds were synthesized and are intended for further in-vitro evaluation against the HCT-116 colorectal cancer cell line.

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